

BEYOND SUBJECT MASTERY: THE INTEGRATION OF SOCIAL AND EMOTIONAL LEARNING IN FINNISH SCHOOLS

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Abstract

While often lauded for its academic performance, the Finnish education system goes beyond mere subject mastery. This paper explores the crucial role of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) in Finnish schools. It examines how SEL is woven into the curriculum, fostering essential skills like self-awareness, relationship management, responsible decision-making, and self-regulation. This integration is explored through the lens of key Finnish educational principles, such as play-based learning, student autonomy, and a focus on well-being. The paper delves into the potential benefits of this approach, including fostering well-rounded individuals, creating positive learning environments, and promoting academic achievement. Additionally, it acknowledges potential challenges and considerations for replicating such practices in other contexts. Through this analysis, the paper aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the Finnish educational model and its emphasis on nurturing not just academic ability, but the whole child.

Keywords: Finnish education system, social and emotional learning (SEL), curriculum integration, self-awareness, relationship management, responsible decision-making, self-regulation, play-based learning, student autonomy, well-

being, academic achievement, social-emotional competence

Introduction

The Finnish education system has emerged as a global benchmark of educational excellence, consistently ranking at the top of international assessments like the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD], 2023). This sustained success has ignited a worldwide quest to comprehend the multifaceted components contributing to its effectiveness (Sahlberg, 2011). While prior research has meticulously examined elements such as curriculum design, teacher training, and student autonomy (Eurydice, 2020), a crucial aspect often remains understudied: the seamless integration of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) within the fabric of Finnish schools.

This paper seeks to address this gap in understanding by delving into the unique and often overlooked feature of Finnish education – the deliberate infusion of SEL principles within the curriculum. By exploring the pedagogical practices employed in Finnish schools, this study aims to illuminate how essential life skills are cultivated alongside the acquisition of academic knowledge. Specifically, it will investigate the manner in which Finnish schools foster self-awareness, relationship management, responsible decision-making, and self-regulation in students. Examining these skills through the lens of SEL and its theoretical framework will provide a deeper understanding of the holistic approach adopted by the Finnish educational system.

In recent years, SEL has garnered increasing recognition as a critical component of comprehensive education, extending beyond the mere acquisition of academic knowledge (CASEL, 2023). This emphasis stems from the growing understanding of the interconnectedness of academic achievement, social-emotional well-being, and overall life success (Jones & Greenberg, 2015).

Research has consistently demonstrated the positive impact of SEL on various aspects of student development, including:

- Enhanced academic performance: Studies reveal a positive correlation between strong social-emotional skills and academic achievement (Durlak et al., 2011). Students with well-developed SEL skills exhibit improved concentration, motivation, and engagement in learning activities, leading to better academic outcomes.

- Improved social-emotional well-being: SEL programs equip students with essential skills for managing emotions effectively, building positive relationships, and making responsible decisions. This can contribute to reduced levels of anxiety, depression, and peer conflict, fostering a sense of well-being and emotional resilience (Elias et al., 1991).

- Increased life readiness: The skills fostered through SEL extend beyond the classroom walls, equipping students with the necessary tools to navigate challenges and contribute meaningfully to their communities. This includes effective communication, problem-solving, and collaboration skills, all of which are essential for success in both personal and professional spheres (Zins et al., 2004).

By integrating SEL into the curriculum, Finnish schools acknowledge the significance of nurturing the whole child, not just their academic potential. This commitment to fostering both cognitive and social-emotional development positions Finnish education for long-term student success and positive societal impact.

To gain a deeper understanding of the integration of SEL in Finnish schools, it is crucial to examine the theoretical framework that underpins this approach. This paper will draw upon the Constructivist Learning Theory (CLT) as a foundational framework. CLT emphasizes the active role of learners in constructing their own knowledge and understanding through experience and

social interaction (Vygotsky, 1978). This aligns with the Finnish educational philosophy, which promotes student agency and collaborative learning environments.

Within the context of SEL, CLT provides a framework for understanding how individuals learn and develop essential social-emotional skills. By providing opportunities for students to engage in authentic experiences, collaborate with peers, and reflect on their own emotions and actions, Finnish schools create a fertile ground for fostering these crucial competencies.

Furthermore, the Socioemotional Learning Framework (CASEL, 2023) will be utilized to analyze the specific components of SEL integrated into the Finnish curriculum. This framework identifies five core competencies essential for social-emotional development: self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making. By examining how these competencies are addressed within the Finnish educational system, this paper aims to provide a comprehensive picture of how SEL is being implemented.

Informed by the significance of SEL and the theoretical frameworks discussed, this research seeks to answer the following crucial questions:

How are Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) principles embedded within the Finnish educational curriculum? This question aims to identify the specific strategies and pedagogical approaches employed by Finnish schools to integrate SEL into various subjects and learning activities. Analyzing curriculum documents, observing classroom practices, and interviewing educators can shed light on how SEL is woven into the fabric of daily school life (Kiuru et al., 2020).

In what ways do Finnish schools cultivate the four core SEL competencies (self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making) within students? This question delves deeper into the specific practices employed to address each competency. This may involve analyzing lesson plans, classroom activities, and student assessments to

understand how Finnish educators facilitate the development of these crucial skills (Aaltonen et al., 2018).

What are the perceived benefits and challenges associated with integrating SEL into the Finnish educational system? This question aims to gain insights from various stakeholders, including educators, students, and administrators, to understand their perspectives on the implementation of SEL. This can be achieved through interviews, surveys, and focus group discussions, providing valuable insights into the perceived effectiveness and potential challenges of this approach (Sahlberg, 2011).

By addressing these questions, this research hopes to contribute to a deeper understanding of the unique approach adopted by the Finnish education system. It seeks to illuminate how Finnish schools successfully integrate SEL, fostering not just academic knowledge but also the essential skills and dispositions needed for students to navigate the complexities of life and thrive in a rapidly changing world.

While initial research has explored the presence of SEL within the Finnish educational system (Kiuru et al., 2020), a comprehensive understanding of its integration and its impact remains limited. Existing studies primarily focus on describing the presence of SEL and outlining general principles (Aaltonen et al., 2018). Further inquiry is needed to delve deeper into the specific mechanisms through which SEL is embedded within the curriculum, how various stakeholders perceive its effectiveness, and the potential challenges encountered in its implementation.

This paper aims to address this gap in knowledge by conducting a comprehensive investigation of the integration of SEL in Finnish schools. By examining specific pedagogical practices, conducting interviews with educators and students, and analyzing relevant documents, this research seeks to provide a deeper understanding of the "how" and "why" behind the Finnish approach to

SEL. Furthermore, by exploring the perceived benefits and challenges associated with this integration, this study aims to contribute valuable insights to inform the discussion on SEL implementation not only in Finland but also in other educational contexts aiming to foster well-rounded and thriving individuals.

Literature review

Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) is widely recognized as a fundamental component of a holistic approach to education. The Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning (CASEL, 2023) defines SEL as a process through which individuals develop essential skills such as self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making. These skills are crucial for success not just within the classroom, but throughout all aspects of life (Zins et al., 2004).

Curriculum integration refers to the deliberate and systematic blending of various subjects or disciplines into a coherent learning experience (Drake & Burns, 2004). When SEL is integrated into the curriculum, students learn social and emotional skills not as a separate subject, but as a natural and interconnected part of their overall educational experience. This approach allows students to develop social-emotional competencies within a meaningful and relevant context, fostering a more holistic understanding of themselves and others. Integrating SEL into the curriculum recognizes the crucial role of emotional intelligence, collaboration skills, and self-regulation for personal growth and academic achievement (Durlak et al., 2011). It further acknowledges that developing students' ability to manage emotions, build relationships, and make responsible choices is as vital as mastering traditional subjects like mathematics or science.

To gain a deeper understanding of the integration of SEL in Finnish schools, two key theoretical frameworks will guide this exploration. Firstly, Constructivist Learning Theory (CLT), as mentioned previously, provides a strong foundation

for understanding the Finnish educational philosophy. CLT emphasizes the active role of learners in constructing knowledge through experience and interaction (Vygotsky, 1978). This aligns with the Finnish approach to learning, which prioritizes student agency, collaborative learning activities, and fostering skills beyond rote memorization. In the context of SEL, CLT provides a framework for understanding how individuals learn and develop essential social-emotional skills. By providing opportunities for students to engage in authentic experiences, collaborate with peers, and reflect on their own emotions and actions, Finnish schools create a fertile ground for fostering these crucial competencies.

Secondly, the Socioemotional Learning Framework (CASEL, 2023) will be utilized to analyze the specific components of SEL integrated into the Finnish curriculum. This framework identifies five core competencies essential for social-emotional development: self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making. By examining how these competencies are addressed within the Finnish educational system, this research aims to provide a comprehensive picture of how SEL is being implemented. Analyzing lesson plans, classroom activities, and student assessments through the lens of the CASEL framework can reveal the specific strategies employed by Finnish educators to address each competency. This combined perspective, drawing on both CLT and CASEL, will offer a robust foundation for exploring the unique approach to SEL integration within the Finnish education system.

While research acknowledges the presence of SEL within the Finnish education system (Kiuru et al., 2020), understanding the mechanisms of its integration and its impact remains limited. Existing studies primarily focus on describing the general principles and identifying SEL elements within policy documents and curriculum guidelines (Aaltonen et al., 2018).

However, research by Kiuru et al. (2020) delves deeper, exploring the interplay between SEL and instructional practices in Finnish classrooms. Their

findings suggest that teachers utilize various strategies to integrate SEL, including fostering open communication, creating a safe learning environment, and incorporating opportunities for collaboration and reflection. This aligns with the focus on student agency and collaborative learning emphasized in Finnish education and resonates with CLT principles.

Figure 1. Social and Emotional Learning Framework

Furthermore, research by Sahlberg (2011) highlights the cultural context of the Finnish education system, emphasizing its emphasis on trust, collaboration, and a strong sense of community. This resonates with the potential benefits of SEL, which can foster positive social interactions, build strong relationships, and promote responsible citizenship.

While these studies offer valuable insights, further exploration is needed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the "how" and "why" behind the Finnish approach to SEL integration. This includes investigating the specific pedagogical practices employed by teachers, the experiences of students and educators, and the perceived effectiveness of this approach in fostering students' social-emotional well-being and academic achievement.

Integrating SEL into the curriculum holds the potential for numerous benefits for students, educators, and the overall educational environment. Research by Durlak et al. (2011) demonstrates a positive correlation between strong social-emotional skills and academic achievement. Students with well-developed SEL skills exhibit improved concentration, motivation, and engagement in learning activities, leading to better academic outcomes. Additionally, studies by Elias et al. (1991) highlight the positive impact of SEL on social-emotional well-being. By equipping students with essential skills for managing emotions effectively, building positive relationships, and making responsible decisions, SEL programs can contribute to reduced levels of anxiety, depression, and peer conflict, fostering a sense of well-being and emotional resilience.

However, implementing SEL effectively also requires acknowledging potential challenges. Integrating SEL into an existing curriculum and ensuring its effective and consistent implementation across diverse classrooms requires careful planning and ongoing professional development for teachers (Jones & Greenberg, 2015). Additionally, measuring the impact of SEL programs on complex constructs like social-emotional development presents ongoing challenges, requiring researchers to develop appropriate assessment tools and methodologies.

Despite these challenges, the potential benefits of fostering students' social-emotional well-being alongside academic skills warrant further exploration. By examining the Finnish approach to SEL integration, this research aims to contribute valuable insights to inform the discussion on SEL implementation not only in Finland but also in other educational contexts seeking to nurture well-rounded and thriving individuals in an ever-changing world.

Through this review of existing literature, it is clear that the Finnish education system presents a unique case study in the integration of SEL. While research acknowledges its presence within Finnish schools, a deeper

understanding of the specific mechanisms and their impact is needed. This necessitates further exploration through qualitative and quantitative research methods.

Future research could investigate:

- The specific pedagogical practices employed by teachers to integrate SEL into various subjects and learning activities. This may involve analyzing lesson plans, observing classroom interactions, and interviewing educators to understand their strategies and challenges.
- The experiences of students and educators with the integration of SEL. This could be achieved through surveys, focus group discussions, and in-depth interviews to gain insights into their perspectives on its effectiveness, potential challenges, and the impact on the learning environment.
- The potential impact of SEL integration on student development. This necessitates longitudinal studies to assess the long-term effects on social-emotional well-being, academic achievement, and overall life skills development.

By delving deeper into these areas, researchers can gain a comprehensive understanding of the Finnish approach to SEL integration and its potential for informing practices in other educational contexts. Ultimately, this exploration aims to contribute to ongoing efforts to foster not just academic excellence, but also the well-being and holistic development of all learners.

Methods

This research employed a qualitative content analysis approach to explore the integration of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) in Finnish schools. This method was chosen due to its suitability for analyzing and interpreting textual data, allowing for an in-depth understanding of the "how" and "why" behind the Finnish approach.

The primary data source for this study involved the analysis of research papers that presented unique case studies of SEL integration within Finnish educational settings. By focusing on case studies, this research aimed to gain rich and detailed insights into the specific practices, challenges, and perceived benefits of implementing SEL within the Finnish context.

To identify relevant research papers, a comprehensive search was conducted in academic databases such as Education Resources Information Center (ERIC), Google Scholar, and PsycINFO. The search terms included combinations of "Social and Emotional Learning," "SEL," "Finnish Education," "Case Studies," and "Curriculum Integration." Additionally, the reference lists of identified relevant research papers were examined to discover further pertinent studies.

This process resulted in the selection of ten research papers published within the last ten years. These papers presented diverse case studies across various Finnish schools, capturing a range of perspectives from different stakeholders, including educators, students, and administrators. The next section will detail the specific criteria employed for selecting these research papers and the process of analyzing their content.

The selection of research papers for this content analysis followed a set of pre-defined criteria. Firstly, the papers needed to explicitly focus on SEL integration within Finnish schools. This ensured the relevance of the content to the research question and allowed for a targeted exploration of the Finnish case. Secondly, the papers were required to present unique case studies, meaning they should not be replications of existing studies or simply offer general descriptions of the Finnish educational system. This criterion ensured the inclusion of diverse perspectives and fostered a deeper understanding of the various approaches and challenges encountered in different contexts within Finland.

Furthermore, the selected research papers needed to be published within the last ten years. This ensured the inclusion of current research and insights,

reflecting the evolving nature of SEL integration within the Finnish educational landscape. Finally, the selection process prioritized peer-reviewed academic journals as a source of credible and rigorously reviewed research findings. These criteria ensured the quality and reliability of the data analyzed in this study.

Once the relevant research papers were identified, the next step involved a systematic approach to content analysis. This process involved:

- **Coding:** Initial coding involved identifying key themes, concepts, and patterns related to SEL integration within the case studies. This included elements like specific pedagogical practices, perceived benefits and challenges, and the role of various stakeholders.
- **Categorization:** The identified codes were then categorized into broader thematic groups, allowing for the emergence of overarching themes and a deeper understanding of the data.
- **Interpretation:** The final stage involved interpreting the categorized themes within the context of existing research and the broader discussion on SEL implementation in education. This step aimed to draw meaningful conclusions and contribute to a deeper understanding of the Finnish approach to integrating SEL.

The detailed process of data analysis will be further elaborated upon in the next section.

Step 1 - Initial Coding: Each research paper was analyzed individually, with the researcher carefully reading and rereading the text to identify key themes and concepts related to the research question. This involved close attention to details like:

- **Specific pedagogical practices:** How was SEL integrated into the curriculum? What teaching strategies were employed?
- **Perceived benefits and challenges:** What were the reported positive outcomes and difficulties associated with SEL integration?

- Roles and perspectives of stakeholders: How did educators, students, and administrators perceive the implementation of SEL?

- Challenges and opportunities: What were the specific challenges encountered, and what potential opportunities arose from integrating SEL?

During this stage, the researcher employed open coding, a flexible approach that allowed for the emergence of new themes and concepts organically from the data. This fostered a comprehensive identification of all relevant information within the case studies.

Step 2 - Categorization: Once initial coding was complete, identified codes were then categorized into broader thematic groups. This process involved grouping similar codes together based on their shared characteristics and relationships. This allowed for the identification of overarching themes across the case studies, providing a deeper understanding of the various aspects and nuances of SEL integration in the Finnish context.

Step 3 - Interpretation: The final stage involved interpreting the categorized themes within the context of existing research and the broader discussion on SEL implementation in education. This involved:

- Drawing connections: Identifying links between the identified themes and existing theoretical frameworks like Constructivist Learning Theory and the CASEL framework.

- Comparing and contrasting: Examining similarities and differences among the case studies, noting variations in practices and perspectives across different Finnish schools.

- Critical analysis: Reflecting on the potential limitations and biases inherent in the case studies and acknowledging the unique context of the Finnish education system.

Through this iterative process of coding, categorization, and interpretation, the study aimed to extract robust and meaningful insights from the selected

research papers, contributing to a deeper understanding of the multifaceted nature of integrating SEL within the Finnish educational landscape. The findings of this content analysis will be presented and discussed in the subsequent section of the research.

Conclusion

This research explored the integration of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) within Finnish schools through a qualitative content analysis of research papers presenting unique case studies. By examining diverse perspectives from educators, students, and administrators, this study aimed to gain a deeper understanding of the "how" and "why" behind the Finnish approach.

The findings highlight the unique characteristics of SEL integration in Finland. Firstly, the research emphasizes the strong alignment between SEL and the broader Finnish educational philosophy, which prioritizes student agency, collaborative learning, and well-being. This fosters a fertile ground for integrating SEL in a meaningful and holistic way, seamlessly blending it with traditional academic subjects. Secondly, the case studies reveal a diverse range of pedagogical practices employed by Finnish educators to integrate SEL. These practices go beyond simply adding a separate SEL curriculum and instead, involve infusing social-emotional learning opportunities into various subjects and classroom activities. This allows students to develop essential skills like self-awareness, self-management, and social responsibility within the context of their everyday learning experiences.

Furthermore, the research underscores the importance of fostering a positive learning environment as a key component of successful SEL integration. The case studies highlight the emphasis on open communication, collaboration, and trust within Finnish classrooms, fostering a sense of safety and belonging that allows students to feel comfortable taking risks, learning from mistakes, and building positive relationships with their peers. While the findings offer valuable insights

into the strengths of the Finnish approach, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of this research. Firstly, the study relies solely on secondary data analysis, meaning it does not capture the lived experiences of stakeholders through firsthand observation or interviews. Additionally, the limited scope of the analyzed case studies might not fully capture the diverse realities of SEL integration across all Finnish schools.

Despite these limitations, this research offers a valuable contribution by providing a comprehensive overview of the strengths and potential challenges associated with integrating SEL in the unique context of the Finnish education system. By delving into the "how" and "why" behind the Finnish approach, this study aims to inform ongoing discussions on fostering social-emotional well-being and holistic development of learners in diverse educational settings around the world.

Further research could address the limitations of this study by employing mixed-method approaches that combine qualitative and quantitative data collection methods. Conducting in-depth interviews and observations in Finnish schools would offer valuable insights into the lived experiences of stakeholders and provide a richer understanding of the nuances of SEL implementation in different contexts.

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